

**ASSIGNMENT
OF
INFORMATION SOURCES AND SERVICES(PRACTICE)**

**TOPIC-THE STATESMAN'S YEARBOOK-2020
THE POLITICS, CULTURES AND ECONOMIES OF THE WORLD**

SUBMITTED TO:

**Dr. PREETI MAHAJAN
Professor, DLIS**

SUBMITTED BY:

**RICHA
CLASS - M.Lib.I.Sc.
SEMESTER - 1ST**

**DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE
PANJAB UNIVERSITY, CHANDIGARH**

PREFACE

It was in the middle of the 19th century that the then British Prime Minister, Robert Peel, suggested to Alexander Macmillan that he should publish 'a handbook presenting in a compact shape a picture of the actual conditions, political and social, of the various states in the civilised world'. The first edition of *The Statesman's Yearbook* was eventually published in January 1864.

Our 155th edition covers Donald Trump's first full year in office as president of the USA and looks at Brexit developments in the UK. The past year also saw the unexpected departures of long-standing leaders Robert Mugabe from the presidency in Zimbabwe and just a few months later Jacob Zuma in South Africa. The entries on both countries include detailed profiles of their successors.

We've added for almost every country a ranking of stability and vulnerability to conflict or collapse taken from the Fragile States Index prepared by the Fund for Peace and *Foreign*

Policy magazine. Another special new feature that we're including this year is a guest article by a renowned academic and Palgrave Macmillan author—Roger Kanet, professor of political science at the University of Miami. He has written a synopsis of his book '*The Russian Challenge to the European Security Environment*', which was published in 2017.

With more than 150 years of history, *The Statesman's Yearbook* has an illustrious past, and all our previous editions are available as individual eBooks. They are also part of Palgrave's and Springer's eBook collections. For details see <http://www.palgrave.com/series/15683>.

We always welcome feedback on the book. Please email us on sybcomments@palgrave.com

Nicholas Heath-Brown
Publisher, *The Statesman's Yearbook*

EVALUATION OF THE STATESMAN'S YEARBOOK 2020

BIBLIOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

Book Title	The Statesman's Yearbook 2020
Book Subtitle	The Politics, Cultures and Economies of the World
Series Title	The Statesman's Yearbook

AUTHORITY

Editors	Palgrave Macmillan
Publisher	Palgrave Macmillan, U.K.

IMPRINT INFORMATION

Name of Publisher	Palgrave Macmillan	
Place of Publication	Basingstoke, United Kingdom	
Year of Publication	First Edition	1864
	Latest Edition	2 nd Oct, 2019 (2020 Edition) (156th)

Other Information

Language	English
Periodicity	Annual

INTRODUCTION

The first edition of The Statesman's Yearbook was inspired by the historian and essayist Thomas Carlyle. His proposal was enthusiastically supported by William Gladstone. Their vision for the book was an authoritative and accessible volume containing information essential for diplomats, politicians and all those involved with international affairs. It quickly gained recognition as an indispensable reference tool and has been published annually since 1864. The editor of 1st edition is Frederick Martin.

The statesman's Yearbook is considered as a classic reference book. It is one volume reference book providing accurate and comprehensive (broad or complete) information on the current politics, cultures, economies and social status of every country in the world.

In 2019, the latest edition (156th) of the statesman's Yearbook is published. It contains information of the world of international affairs, there are also splendid (brilliant, excellent of a very high standard) world maps and flags of the world. This book remains the first point of reference of reliable, concise information on any country in the world. It was ranked by library journal as the top 20 best reference resources.

SCOPE

It is international in scope.

- The main purpose of this book is to cover current events, factual information and day to day happenings.
- It provide Revised and updated biographical profiles of all current leaders.
- It provides Week-by-week chronology of key political events from March 2018 to February 2019.
- It provide Comprehensive coverage of major international organizations.
- 2018 in 1,000 words—a summary of the key events that dominated the world during the year.
- It provide extensive updates to country economic overviews.
- It provide expanded and updated historical introductions.
- It is preeminent and most comprehensive ready-reference source for current material about countries worldwide.
- The scope has become broader, with expended coverage of history, politics, economics, trade and infrastructure for each country.

TREATMENT

It contains Time zones, Maps, The Rise and Rise of Population by Bary Turner, World Population developments, largest urban agglomerations, key world facts, recommended further readings, chronology.

it is mainly divided into two parts: Part 1- International organisation and Part 2- Countries of the world (A-Z).

PART 1: International Organizations

International Organizations has information about various organizations in the world. Information about their origin, history, aims and activities, organizational members, capital resources, agencies, finance, language, headquarters, website and email address, relations with worlds other organizations and countries.

PART 2: Countries of the World (A - Z)

A-Z: Key Historical Events, Territory and Population, Social Statistics, Climate, Constitution and Government, Government Chronology ,Recent Elections, Current Government, Current leaders, defence, Economy , Energy and Natural Resources, Environment, Industry, International Trade, Communications, Social Institutions, Culture, Diplomatic Representatives, Further Readings.

- It contains select sources of Statesman's yearbook, Abbreviations, current leaders Index, Place and International Organizations Index.

ARRANGEMENT

- The wealth of information is arranged in a logical and consistent manner.
- It is divided into two parts i.e. Part 1 and Part 2.
- In Part 1 International Organizations of world, Organizations of Europe Americans, Asia/Pacific, Middle East, Africa and other organizations of the world has been included and arranged according to continents.
- In Part 2 All the 194 countries of the world are arranged in alphabetical order (letter by letter).
- Index is arranged in alphabetical order (letter by letter).

FORMAT

Print Format :

- **Size :** It is a Single Volume reference book, handy and easy to consult.
- **Typography :** Printing is clear and legible, headings are in bold face and descriptive information, reasonable space between the letters, words, and lines.
- **Columns :** Information is given in two columns.
- **Paper :** Good quality paper is used.
- **Binding:** It is available in Hardcover binding.
- **Illustrations:** Maps and tables are given. 4 Illustrations in colour; 1 black and white illustration.

ONLINE FORMAT :

The statesman's Yearbook also available in online version since 2002 and updated regularly. It can be accessible on subscription based via the website : www.statesmansyearbook.com or <https://link.springer.com> .

- ◇ Online resource contains the complete archive from 1864 to 2018 was added to the website, full text and additional content, which includes: Fact Sheets on topics including world population development, News Media, Crime and Health, economic overviews.
- ◇ Comparison tool which makes it easy to view a wide range of data fields across all the countries of the world in one place.
- ◇ Improved interface with new homepage.
- ◇ Offers excellent search and browse facilities, dynamic searching of countries, quick search on every page which makes it easier to explore the Yearbook.
- ◇ Advanced search features include Headings, both Full text and Abstract, Names of people in headings, Bibliographies, Countries etc.
- ◇ Citation, total no of downloads and further readings(for cross references) listed on every page.
- ◇ Allows remote access to members of subscribing institutions.

SPECIAL FEATURES

- Barry Turner investigates democracy's origins and role in the modern world, plus a factsheet on democracy throughout history.
- Civil and criminal justice rankings, plus updated corruption rankings are provided.
- Part II of the yearbook contains maps of each country with its position in the world.
- Statistics on access to clean water worldwide.
- Population projections for every country in 2020.
- World rankings of social and political stability.

DRAWBACKS

- The statesman's Yearbook is biased towards UK.
- Every year such a huge amount of information is generated which is impossible for a yearbook in single volume to cover.
- It cannot convey cultures unique perspective.

CONCLUSION

The statesman's yearbook covers current events, factual information and day to day happenings. It is an invaluable source of reliable and concise information in the world of international affairs. It satisfy the needs of the population of various states and countries, officials, exports, constitutions, governments, diplomatic representatives, religion, finance, and basic histories. "It is an essential tool of all global thinking" - Geographical Magazine. The Statesman's Yearbook which is an *Encyclopaedic Yearbook*, deals with international matters including international organizations and countries of the world. Its purpose is to inform people with most recent data of international affairs. The Statesman's Yearbook served as an excellent and most reliable up-to-date source even more than a hundred years ago. It will save hours of research and cross-referencing between different sources. It should be an essential annual purchase for any university library.

REFERENCES

- <https://www.palgrave.com/in/book/9781137508522#aboutAuthors>
- <https://www.bookdepository.com/Statesmans-Yearbook-2020-Palgrave-MacMillan/9781137508522>
- <https://link.springer.com/referencework/10.1007/978-1-349-70154-4#toc>
- <https://www.springer.com/in/book/9781349953202#aboutAuthors>
- <https://www.amazon.com/Statesmans-Yearbook-2020-Politics-Economies/dp/1349953202>